

Migration Policy in Germany in a Demographic Crisis

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Abstract: This article analyzes the migration policy and technologies used by Germany to overcome the demographic crisis. Strategies to attract innovative technologies and skilled migrants to support labor shortages and an aging population are discussed. At the same time, the problems arising as a result of the migration process are also studied.

Keywords: Demographic crisis, Germany, migration policy, skilled migration act, digitization.

A demographic crisis is a situation that describes changes in the natural growth or decline of the population, characterized by a decrease in the number of people as a result of a decrease in the birth rate and an increase in life expectancy. This phenomenon has become one of the urgent issues for many developed and developing countries today. For example, according to the World Bank (2022), declining birth rates in European countries threaten the sustainability of economic development, as labor shortages in the labor market slow down economic growth and strain the social security system. imposes additional pressure. Therefore, many countries have started to implement an active migration policy in order to alleviate the consequences of the demographic crisis.

The causes of the demographic crisis are diverse and are related to social, economic and cultural factors. Declining birth rate is one of the main reasons. For example, according to the United Nations (UN, 2023), the average female fertility rate in developed countries has fallen below 2.1, which is not enough to maintain the population at a stable level. This situation is observed especially in countries such as Germany, Japan and Italy. The second reason is the aging of the population. Thanks to advances in medicine, life expectancy has increased in many developed countries. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2021), as the average life expectancy increases, the proportion of elderly people is increasing, which leads to a reduction in the working age population in economic systems. This trend also has a negative impact on economic development, because the lack of sufficient labor force in the labor market reduces the rate of economic growth.

The following problem can be mentioned as an important issue of the research on this topic: "In the conditions of the demographic crisis, the migration policy of the states is successful enough to effectively fill the gaps in the labor market and ensure economic stability, but in the process of social integration of immigrants, they face the coming difficulties have a negative impact on the overall effectiveness of this policy. At the same time, immigrants visiting these countries face serious problems such as cultural adaptation, social isolation, employment difficulties, discrimination and xenophobia.

The importance of studying this problem is that the migration policy of states is necessary not only to ensure economic growth, but also to maintain social balance. If the country is able to support the economy through the migration policy, the process of social integration between the immigrants and the local population is unsuccessful, this may cause social tension, ethnic conflicts and national security issues in the future. Such integration difficulties are especially evident in countries such as Germany and Russia (Federal Migration Service of Russia, 2022; European Commission, 2022).

Germany's demographic crisis has made migration policy an important focus in the country, as Germany faces complex challenges such as low birth rates, high death rates and an aging population. Migration has become an important tool for maintaining a stable population and supporting economic and social systems in Germany. Every aspect of Germany's migration strategy, including policy principles and targeted labor recruitment, aims to fill labor shortages, ease the burden of an aging population, and ensure economic stability.

Although Germany's population is expected to grow from an estimated 81.69 million in 2015 to 83.24 million in 2022, it is increasing mainly due to migration as natural population growth has stagnated (Table 1). The birth rate fell from 8.6 per 1,000 in 2015 to 7.9 per 1,000 in 2022, while the death rate increased to 12.3 per 1,000 in 2022 (Table 2). Migration flows play a key role in supporting the stability of Germany's population and prevent labor shortages from exacerbating. In this way, Germany's migration policy is not only an economic strategy, but also a necessary demographic factor for the German economy.

(Table 1) Total population in Germany (2015-2022)

Germany's approach to migration has evolved significantly in recent years, and the government has introduced policies aimed at attracting skilled labor from abroad. The Skilled Migration Act of 2020 marked a turning point in Germany as it simplified immigration pathways for skilled non-national workers, especially in high-demand sectors such as healthcare, IT and engineering. Under this law, in order to work in Germany, the requirement to first prove that German or EU workers are not eligible for the position was removed. By focusing on skilled migration, Germany fills gaps in its domestic labor market. For example, the healthcare sector is experiencing a shortage of nurses and caregivers due to an aging population, and the influx of skilled labor can help fill this gap. Likewise, the IT sector has been successful in attracting

international talent through this law, supporting Germany's technological development and innovation capabilities.

(Table 2) Birth and Death Rates in Germany (2015-2022)

Net migration rate data show the importance of these policies. Germany had the highest migration rate in 2016 (14.5 per 1,000 people), mainly due to the influx of refugees from countries such as Syria and Afghanistan (Table 3). After this level, the migration rate stabilized and reached 5.2 per 1000 people in 2022. This stability reflects a shift to structural economic migration rather than large-scale humanitarian flows. Despite a decline in migration rates after 2016, Germany maintained a positive net migration rate. This helped to stabilize the population and fill the gaps in the low and semi-skilled sectors of the labor market. The Skilled Migration Act clarifies migration policy to meet Germany's economic and demographic needs and supports economic growth by attracting skilled workers.

(Table 3) Level of Net Migration in Germany (2015-2022)

Germany's aging population is increasing the need for young, economically active migrants. By 2022, those over 65 years of age accounted for 24 percent of the population, a significant increase from 21.1 percent in 2015 (Table 4). This demographic change increases the specific burden factor, which puts pressure on Germany's pension and health care systems, meaning that fewer workers must support more pensioners. Migration helps to solve this problem by bringing young, labor force individuals into the country. Skilled migrants, in particular, increase tax payments and support an aging population, which is important for maintaining economic stability. Thus, Germany uses its migration policy to solve economic and demographic problems and helps support social welfare systems.

(Table 4) Share of the 65+ population in Germany (2015-2022)

However, the success of the migration policy lies not only in the influx of skilled migrants, but also in their integration. Migrants' ability to enter the labor market and contribute to the economy depends on how well they adapt. Germany has developed programs to help migrants integrate into the labor force, including language learning, vocational training, and foreign degree recognition. Language proficiency has a direct impact on employment outcomes; Migrants who are fluent in German have the opportunity to enter high-paying jobs, especially in areas that require effective communication, such as health care. The integration framework is designed to increase the contribution of migrants to the economy, enabling them to succeed in the sectors they are involved in and to maximize their contribution to the German economy.

Germany's unemployment rate is low, ranging from 3.2 percent to 4.3 percent from 2015 to 2022, indicating strong demand for labor in various sectors. This demand is most significant in sectors such as manufacturing, hospitality, and especially healthcare, where labor shortages are strongest. Germany's aging population increases the demand for healthcare workers as more elderly people need care. Migration policies, especially programs aimed at attracting health workers from abroad, meet these requirements. Germany's migration policy is aimed not only at filling job vacancies, but also at retaining these migrants as long-term economic partners.

For a broader review of Germany's demographic crisis and migration policy, it is necessary to cite scientific studies conducted by well-known researchers and logical connections between them. According to the study "Integrating Migrants in Germany: Successes and Challenges" (2021) by Thomas Liebig and Thomas Huddleston, Germany's integration policy is a decisive factor for improving the economic performance of migrants. They emphasize that language and

vocational training programs play an important role in the integration process. Liebig and Huddleston's research shows that while the Skilled Migration Act has made it easier for highly skilled workers to enter Germany, the integration process, especially among refugees, is complex and fraught with obstacles. They note that the biggest problems facing refugees in Germany are language barriers and lack of education. Their research confirms that the level of language knowledge and skills of refugees are directly related to the economic activity of refugees. In situations where skilled workers can fill particularly high-demand industries, such as technology and health care, a high level of language proficiency can help them succeed in these industries. But Liebig and Huddleston point out that refugees whose qualifications are not recognized by German employers are often drawn into low-paid and temporary jobs. This suggests that Germany's integration strategy should be further strengthened and expanded to support the economic integration of refugees (Libig & Huddleston, 2021).

Herbert Brücker, a researcher at the German Institute for Employment Research (IAB), conducted a leading study analyzing the labor market impact of refugees entering Germany in 2015–2016. Brücker's work, *Economic and Labor Market Impact of Refugee Integration in Germany* (2021), finds that although almost half of refugees will be employed by 2021, most of them will be employed in low-skilled jobs. This means that opportunities for upward mobility among refugees are limited due to language barriers and difficulties in recognizing foreign qualifications (Brukker, 2021). According to Brooker's analysis, refugees fill labor gaps, especially in manual and high-demand sectors, but their integration is hampered by systemic problems. Brooker notes that, economically, refugees' contribution will increase over time and that with additional vocational training, they can find a place in the labor market. This indicates the need for the state to invest in permanent integration programs to unlock the full economic potential of refugees (Bruker, 2021).

Demographic Change and Migration: Germany's Need for a Skilled Workforce (2020) by Holger Hinte, Ulf Rinne, and Klaus F. Zimmermann examines the economic impact of Germany's demographic changes and migration policy. With Germany's low birth rate and rising elderly population, the shrinking labor force will put significant pressure on the state's finances, researchers say. They highlight the growing need for skilled young workers, especially to ensure the sustainability of pension and healthcare systems (Hinte, Rinne & Zimmermann, 2020). Their research shows that young and skilled workers are needed to reduce labor shortages in high-need industries such as medicine and information technology. Hinte, Rinne, and Zimmermann argue that Skilled Migration Act policies play an important role, but that these policies need to be supported by programs that support permanent residence and family reunification, which can help attract skilled workers to Germany in the long term. will help.

Christian Dustmann and Tommaso Frattini analyzed the financial impact of migration in Germany and Europe in their study "Financial Impact of Immigration in Germany and Europe" (2019). Dustmann and Frattini find that skilled migrants contribute more to public finances and pay more in taxes than they receive in social benefits. This will have a positive effect on Germany's GDP and will not burden social services. Dustmann and Frattini state that skilled migrants play an important role in Germany's research and innovation sector, accounting for a large proportion of patents and innovations (Dustmann & Frattini, 2019). Their research shows the financial rationale behind Germany's focus on skilled migration policy, as skilled workers not only fill labor gaps, but also boost technological development and competitiveness. Their findings suggest that from a fiscal perspective, skilled migration is a sustainable approach to strengthening Germany's economy, especially given the rising social protection costs associated with an aging population.

Germany is facing a demographic crisis such as an aging population and a low birth rate, and is launching a number of strategic projects and policies to address the challenges posed by these demographic changes. These initiatives focus on long-term solutions, such as supporting

families and increasing birth rates, and on short-term measures, such as accelerating migration to address labor market gaps. One of these projects is the Skilled Migration Act (Fachkräfteinwanderungsgesetz) that came into force in 2020, which simplifies the immigration process for skilled workers from non-EU countries (Federal Ministry of the Interior, 2020). The law removes some bureaucratic hurdles, such as the requirement to give priority to German or EU citizens for certain jobs, and speeds up the process of hiring skilled workers from outside the EU. The act allowed Germany to attract workers with critical skills needed to maintain its economy and health care systems, which are facing critical shortages due to an aging population.

Another important project is Germany's investment in family support policies aimed at increasing the birth rate. Programs such as Elterngeld and Elternzeit provide new parents with financial support and job retention, thereby helping families grow (Federal Statistical Office, 2021). These policies create incentives for paid parental leave and temporary leave from work for both parents, and create a family environment that supports child care. Despite these efforts, Germany's fertility rate remains relatively low: from 8.6 births per 1,000 in 2015 to 7.9 per 1,000 in 2022 (Destatis, 2022), supporting families -suggests that support policies alone may have limited effectiveness in reversing demographic decline.

Another important initiative is the Demographic Strategy developed by the German Federal Government. This strategy, updated in 2021, includes goals such as strengthening rural areas, improving care and health for the elderly, and supporting families and young people. By investing in regional development, this strategy aims to prevent the emptying of rural areas and promote a balanced demographic distribution. The Demographic Strategy also emphasizes the importance of integrating migrants into the labor force to reduce labor market gaps throughout the country, not just in urban centers (Federal Ministry of the Interior, 2021).

Germany's migration policy has become central to its strategy to combat demographic decline. The positive net migration rate played an important role in maintaining the country's population despite natural declines. In 2016, the migration rate reached 14.5 per 1,000 people due to the influx of refugees during the Syrian crisis. Although migration levels have stabilized since then, Germany still recorded a positive result of 5.2 per 1,000 people in 2022, which played an important role in compensating for low birth rates and high death rates (Federal Statistical Office, 2022). This migration flow has played an important role in maintaining population stability and mitigating labor shortages exacerbated by an aging population.

One of the most notable outcomes of Germany's migration policy is its impact on the labor market. The Skilled Migration Act has been successful in attracting highly skilled professionals, particularly in the healthcare, IT and engineering sectors. For example, the health sector has seen an influx of nurses and care workers from countries outside the EU, which has helped to reduce severe labor shortages in this important sector (OECD, 2021). The IT sector has also benefited greatly, as skilled migrants have taken on roles essential to Germany's technological development, such as cyber security, software development and data science. These results show the effectiveness of Germany's migration policy in filling gaps in the labor market that limit economic growth.

In addition to economic benefits, Germany's migration policy also has a positive financial impact. Skilled migrants pay more in taxes than they receive in social benefits, which helps support Germany's welfare system. According to the OECD, skilled migrants, especially those working in STEM (science, technology, engineering and mathematics) fields, have played an important role in driving innovation and contributing to national GDP through higher productivity and economic activity (OECD, 2021). Migrants' financial contributions help offset the high costs of pensions and health care for an aging population.

In addition, migration contributes to Germany's research and development sectors. Skilled migrants in STEM and healthcare fields account for a large proportion of patents and

innovations, which increase Germany's global competitiveness and play an important role in the country's scientific and technological leadership. According to the German Economic Institute (IW), about 15 percent of patents granted in Germany in recent years were granted by foreign-born experts, indicating the important place of migrants in Germany's technological and scientific development (IW, 2022).

Despite the success of Germany's migration policy, it faces serious challenges in the field of integration. One of the main challenges is that while policies aimed at attracting skilled migrants have been effective in attracting talent, integration has become a difficult task, especially for refugees and low-skilled workers. Language barriers, recognition of skills and cultural differences are factors that prevent migrants from fully integrating into the labor market. For example, according to the German Institute for Employment Research (IAB), the refugee influx of 2015-2016 resulted in around 50% of refugees being employed by 2021, but many jobs were low-skilled and low-paid jobs (IAB, 2021). This underemployment problem reflects the difficulty of adapting migrants' skills to the demands of the German labor market, especially for those with less easily recognized qualifications.

The issue of language learning also has a serious impact on the integration of migrants. Although Germany has invested in language courses, many migrants still struggle to master the language, which limits their chances of advancing to higher positions in the labor market. Language skills are especially important in areas where effective communication is required, such as healthcare. To address this problem, Germany has introduced special language programs used in the medical and technical fields, but these programs are not comprehensive enough to meet the demand (Federal Office for Migration and Refugees, 2021).

Retention of skilled migrants is another challenge. Although the Skilled Migration Act has simplified entry, many migrants face difficulties in obtaining permanent residence and family reunification. These problems discourage long-term settlement, as many migrants prefer countries that make it easier to settle and support a family. For this reason, Germany has recently started to think about reforms to facilitate long-term stays for skilled migrants, but concrete policy changes have not yet been developed (Federal Ministry of the Interior, 2021).

The demographic crisis has also created regional differences. Germany's rural areas, where labor shortages are more severe than in urban centers, face difficulties in attracting and retaining migrants. This disparity exacerbates rural population decline, which has serious consequences in areas that already suffer from a lack of infrastructure, health and education opportunities. In response, the Demographic Strategy takes measures to stimulate regional development and attract migrants to live in these areas. However, these measures have had limited success as migrants often prefer the job opportunities and conditions offered by urban centers (Federal Ministry of the Interior, 2021).

At the same time, Germany's migration policy has achieved several key achievements. By attracting a young, skilled workforce, Germany has been able to partially offset the growing burden factor and reduce the burden on social welfare systems. Migrants contribute significantly to sectors with high labor shortages, support the country's economic growth and help maintain competitiveness in high-tech industries. The economic benefits of migration are particularly evident in the health and STEM fields, where migrants play an important role in filling critical gaps and driving innovation.

Germany's migration experience offers valuable lessons for other countries facing demographic challenges. The country's proactive approach to skilled migration has shown that immigration can effectively support economic growth and demographic stability. However, Germany's experience also highlights the importance of overcoming barriers to integration, developing rural areas and providing pathways for long-term livelihoods.

Overall, Germany's response to its demographic crisis highlights the integral role of migration in sustaining economic growth, supporting the labor market and supporting social welfare systems. The Skilled Migration Act and the Demographic Strategy outline Germany's efforts to attract and integrate skilled workers in high-demand sectors. Migration has proven to be an effective tool in offsetting the effects of low birth rates and an aging population, but persistent barriers to the effective integration and long-term retention of migrants remain to be overcome. Although Germany's migration policy has made significant progress, the country still needs to continue adapting its strategies to address ongoing challenges such as language barriers, recognition of skills and regional labor imbalances.

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